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REVIEW ON ACANTHOSIS NIGRICANS**Ramdas Bhat^{1*}, Grinton Veigas² and Jason Fernandes Joekim³**

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ABSTRACT

Acanthosis nigricans (AN) is an uncommon skin condition that involves dermatosis, hyperkeratosis, and skin darkening followed by velvety thickening of the epidermis. It mostly affects the posterior neck fold, axillae, umbilicus and flexor skin surfaces although it can also affect the mucosal surfaces. Despite the fact that the majority of causes are benign, it has been related to gastrointestinal and other cancers. Gastroenterologists, dermatologists, and oncologists all need to collaborate closely. An Acanthosis nigricans is thought to be linked with insulin resistance, a disorder characterised by inadequate physiologic responses to insulin. Insulin resistance, according to some experts, leads to a build-up of the hormone in the blood, which subsequently enters skin cells. Obesity and Type-II diabetes mellitus have both been linked to insulin resistance.

KEYWORDS: Acanthosis nigricans (AN), Type-II Diabetes mellitus, Insulin, Obesity, Malignant Acanthosis nigricans (MAN).

INTRODUCTION

Skin is an endocrine organ that defends the entire body from infection. Skin creates perspiration, which keeps our body cool and protects interior organs. The skin serves as the initial line of defence and protects our body from. Skin is an organ that easily gets prone to infections and tumorous growth.^[1]

Acanthosis nigricans (AN) is a more common sign of systemic disorders that is underappreciated as a distinct dermatological condition. It has a number of characteristics,

including dark-brown hyperpigmentation, localised thickening of the skin, and a velvety texture. The lesions are typically symmetrical, affecting regions of the body with skin folds such as the neck, axillae, forehead, popliteal and antecubital fossae, groin, and umbilicus. The neck is the area that is affected, particularly in children. Potentiator cofactors like as abrasion or sweating can generate AN distribution pattern with greater frequency on the axillae and neck. Mechanical forces have a crucial role in the proliferation of skin keratinocytes, with their influence mediated by complicated cellular signalling.^[2,3]

Other sites that may be affected include the conjunctiva of eye, eyelids, lips, flexor and extensor faces of the knees and elbows, knuckles - anterior face, external genitalia, areolae, inner face of the thighs, and anus. AN may affect the oral mucosa, oesophagus, nose, or larynx in certain cases, specifically when accompanied with malignancies.^[4,5,6]

In 1889, Paul Gerson Unna recorded the first instance of AN in a patient with "widespread pigmentation and papillary hypertrophy," with the designation AN appearing later that year (1891) in writings by Janovsky and Pollitzer.^[7] AN is a skin condition that can be linked to benign endocrine disorders such as obesity and insulin resistance, or it can present as a paraneoplastic symptom in a variety of cancers.^[8,9]

Etiology

There are several etiological variables that contribute to the development of Acanthosis nigricans (AN).^[10]

- Increased circulating insulin, specifically IGF-1, stimulates keratinocyte insulin-like growth factor (ILGF) receptors. Insulin may displace IGF-1 from IGF binding protein at high quantities. Keratinocyte and dermal fibroblast proliferation may be triggered by increased circulating IGF.
- Fibroblast growth factor deficiencies are associated with hereditary variations.
- The mechanism behind malignancy-related Acanthosis nigricans appears to have elevated transforming growth factor levels (TGF). TGF operates on skin epidermal tissue via the epidermal growth factor receptor.

Familial Acanthosis nigricans (AN): It appear at adolescence or during early childhood due to defect in chromosome that is autosomal dominant trait FGF receptor 3 mutations. (FGFR3).^[11]

Obesity-associated acanthosis nigricans (AN): Obesity is one among the common condition associated with Acanthosis nigricans. Lesions are more prevalent in adults, but they can affect anyone at any age. It was previously known as "Pseudoacanthosis nigricans." It could be linked to insulin resistance. Treating obesity with proper diet, exercise, weight loss can prevent the recurrence of Acanthosis nigricans.^[12,13]

Medications associated acanthosis nigricans (AN): AN has been linked to a number of medications. Diethylstilbestrol, Oestrogen, combined oral contraceptives, niacin, Systemic glucocorticoids, Growth hormone therapy and injectable insulin are some of the examples of offending medications. Once such medications are stopped AN get resolved.^[14,15,16]

Acanthosis nigricans (AN) associated with endocrine dysfunction: It takes longer to develop, is less prevalent, and sufferers are often overweight. Insulin-resistance diseases of type A (HAIR-AN) and type B can be differentiated. Hyperandrogenaemia, Acanthosis nigricans, and insulin resistance are all symptoms of Type A syndromes. Type B syndrome is more common in women who have ovarian hyperandrogenism, uncontrolled diabetes, or autoimmune diseases such SLE, Sjogren's syndrome, or scleroderma. Polycystic ovarian syndrome is associated to acanthosis nigricans (PCOS). PCOS patients have hyperandrogenism and insulin resistance.^[17]

Acral acanthotic anomaly: A kind of acanthosis nigricans that affects just the knees, elbows, knuckles, and the dorsal face of the foot. It is very common in those with dark complexion.^[18]

Malignant acanthosis nigricans (MAN): Is associated to gastrointestinal adenocarcinomas, as well as prostate, ovarian, and breast cancer. Acanthosis nigricans is seldom associated to lung cancer and lymphoma. Internal cancer can be preceded, accompanied, or followed by Malignant Acanthosis nigricans (MAN). Multiple seborrheic keratoses (a hallmark of Leser-Trelat), Skin tags and tripe palms are typical signs of MAN.^[19,20]

Auto-immune acanthosis nigricans: AN can be linked to autoimmune diseases such as Sjogren's syndrome, SLE, Hashimoto's thyroiditis, or scleroderma.^[21]

Unilateral acanthosis nigricans: Also known as naevoid Acanthosis nigricans. It is extremely uncommon and is inherited in an autosomal dominant manner. Unilateral lesions appear. Lesions that appear throughout childhood, adolescence, or adulthood.^[22]

Epidemiology

Frequency

United states

Acanthosis nigricans has an unknown prevalence. The alterations of AN were seen in 7.1 percent of an unselected cohort of 1412 children. Acanthosis nigricans is intimately linked to obesity, with more than half of adults who weigh more than 200 percent of their normal body weight having lesions that are acanthosis nigricans-like. The MAN is significantly less prevalent; in one study, just two out of 12,000 cancer patients displayed indications of the disease. The most common connections were with gastrointestinal adenocarcinomas (70-90 percent), notably gastric cancer (55-61 percent of malignant acanthosis nigricans cases).^[23]

International

Epidemiologic studies conducted in the UAE, Japan, and Iran all revealed statistically significant increases in insulin resistance in obese patients with Acanthosis nigricans compared to matched obese controls without Acanthosis nigricans. This states that Acanthosis nigricans is a useful marker for insulin resistance in obese patients regardless of geographic setting.^[24]

Race

People with darker skin pigmentation are more likely to develop acanthosis nigricans. Whites account for less than 1% of the population. According to one research, the frequency is 5.5 percent among Latinos and 13.3 percent among African Americans. The prevalence is considerably higher among Native Americans, with 34.2 percent of Cherokee patients aged 5-40 years having acanthosis nigricans, rising to 73 percent of Cherokee patients with diabetes in one research.^[25,26]

In Latino patients, the proportion of overweight children aged 7 to 17 years rises to 23%, whereas in African American patients it rises to 19.4%. Acanthosis nigricans affects 62 % of children of any race who have a BMI greater than the 98%.^[27,28,29]

Malignant acanthosis nigricans, unlike the benign variety, displays no racial preference.

Sex

AN can be found affecting both the sexes in equal proportion. There is no documented gender preference for Acanthosis nigricans.^[30]

Age

AN is a benign skin disorder that can arise at any age, including infancy, but is more common in adults. MAN is more frequent in the elderly; nonetheless, Wilms tumor, gastric adenocarcinoma, and osteogenic sarcoma have been seen in children.^[30]

Pathophysiology^[31,32]

Increased activation of Growth Factor Receptor Proteins (GFRP) causes AN, which is most commonly caused by endocrine dysfunction. Hyperinsulinemia or insulin resistance, as observed in diabetes mellitus, causes insulin-mediated activation of IGF receptors on keratinocytes.

- Elevated circulating insulin, which plays a role in the progression of AN. As a result, IGF-1 receptors in keratinocytes are activated. If insulin is present in large concentrations, it can displace IGF-1 from the Insulin-like growth factor-binding protein (IGFBP). Increased circulating IGF may assist keratinocyte and cutaneous fibroblast development.
- FGFR (Fibroblast Growth Factor Receptor) abnormalities in hereditary variants of AN.
- Increased transforming growth factor (TGF), which appears to be the cause of acanthosis nigricans linked to malignancy. TGF binds to the epidermal growth factor receptor and affects epidermal tissue (EGFR).
- Perspiration and friction are believed to be required predeterminants for lesions in conjunction with higher end levels of IGF, as insulin is normally insufficient to activate IGF receptors throughout the body.

Signs and Symptoms^[33,34,35]

Hyperpigmentation and hyperkeratosis are the most common Acanthosis nigricans symptoms. Changes in the colour and texture of a person's skin may be seen. It's possible that the colour will change to grey, black, or brown. It's possible that the look and texture may become silky. Changes might take months or even years to manifest. They might be a symptom of malignancy if they occur suddenly. The lesions might potentially be more extensive and visible.

The Signs and Symptoms include

- Dark pigmentation of the skin.

- Pigmentation can be found in skin folds like arm pits, elbows, knees, below the breast and in the groin.
- Thick velvety textured blackish brown patches can be found over the skin.
- Skin tags appear in and around the patchy area.
- Itchiness in the affected area with foul smelling skin.
- Papillomatosis (Finger like projection) formation in the affected mucous membrane.

Figure no. 1: Signs and Symptoms of Acanthosis nigricans.

Figure no. 2: A) Skin showing hyperorthokeratosis, marked papillomatosis, mild acanthosis, and discrete melanic hyperpigmentation of the epidermal basal layer. (B) Areola skin with hyperorthokeratosis, papillomatosis, and acanthosis.

Prognosis^[31]

Acanthosis nigricans is more likely to improve when a recognized cause is eliminated. Acanthosis nigricans which is caused due to obesity, will drastically improve with weight loss, but medication-induced acanthosis nigricans will typically resolve once the treatment is discontinued. Hereditary variations may or may not disappear with age, while cancer-associated variants may disappear when the cancer is eliminated.

Diagnosis^[8,36]

The diagnosis of AN is made clinically, with a skin biopsy providing confirmation. Hyperkeratosis, epidermal folding, melanocyte proliferation in the epidermal basal layer and leukocyte infiltration are all prevalent histological patterns in all types of AN. Hyperpigmentation appears to be caused by thickening and hyperkeratosis rather than an overabundance of melanin. Hyperkeratosis, caused by keratinocyte proliferation, is the most prominent sign of MAN, although hyperpigmentation is minimal.

Treatment^[3]

AN is not a disease, but rather a symptom of a variety of conditions that cannot be treated on its own. The progression of the skin issue is determined by the underlying disease; therefore, AN therapy focuses on the underlying disorder. Following insulin resistance correction (by maintaining a low-calorie diet and persistent physical exercise) or obesity control (through weight loss), some individuals have reported a decrease in hyperkeratosis.

Dermatologists treat AN using retinoids and podophyllin as topical keratolytic, with varying degrees of effectiveness. Laser procedures, chemical peels, and dermabrasion are some of the other cosmetic treatments used. Metformin, tretinoin, and octreotide were used to manage insulin resistance with modest effectiveness. Despite the maintenance of insulin resistance, Giri et al reported full remission of AN after 2 years of metformin treatment.

In addition, rosiglitazone can be used to treat AN induced by insulin resistance. Bellot-Rojas et al. found that rosiglitazone treatment resulted in lower fasting insulin levels than metformin treatment, with both treatments resulting in moderate improvements in skin texture. Metformin therapies that improve insulin resistance and AN are those that last longer than six months. Metformin lowers insulin resistance in the periphery, hyperinsulinemia, glucose production, and body weight. After improving insulin sensitivity in peripheral muscles with a combination of thiazolidinediones and metformin, a favourable response of

AN was seen. In obesity-related AN, melatonin therapy (3 mg/day) has been shown to improve both insulin resistance and pigmentation.

Immunomodulatory regimens include rituximab, dexamethasone, and cyclophosphamide are used to treat AN associated with autoimmune insulin resistance, including antibodies against the insulin receptor or against insulin itself. Cyclosporine A has been proven to have moderate effectiveness in treating generalized AN, with significant decreases in both cutaneous and mucosal papillomatous lesions.

The evolution of paraneoplastic AN is tightly linked to the evolution of cancer, regressing after surgical ablation of the tumor or in some cytostatic therapies; it might even be a helpful measure for therapeutic monitoring, since it reactivates in case of tumor relapse or metastasis development.

In the instance of AN associated with insulinoma, because the tumor is properly confined and surgically treatable, the skin lesion may entirely resolve after the insulinoma is removed. Even after partial pancreatectomy for the HAIR-AN syndrome, there has been a report of full AN remission.

Patient education

Patients should be informed that Acanthosis nigricans is not a skin illness in and of itself, but rather a symptom of an underlying issue. If a patient has Acanthosis nigricans due to insulin resistance, which is the most prevalent cause, treating the metabolic abnormalities may improve the skin's look. Dietary adjustments and weight loss may allow the Acanthosis nigricans to nearly fully resolve.

CONCLUSION

Acanthosis nigricans can be defined as a dermatological condition associated with the systemic manifestations. Acanthosis nigricans can be associated with insulin resistance, Obesity or with Malignancy. The severity of the condition can be mild to moderate depending on the condition with which AN is associated with. Because some cases of AN occur before or at the same time as the primary malignant illness, the physician must conduct a comprehensive examination of the patient in order to rule out the paraneoplastic form. The current study covers the etiopathogenesis and consequences of various AN type, and offers a

new AN classification that might aid in patient diagnosis, risk stratification, and treatment regimen.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

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